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Valentné Albert, É. (2020). A játék profán oldalán túl [Beyond the profane side of play]. *Tudomány és Hivatás*, 5(2), 42–52. Original Hungarian text available via EPA-OSZK:

https://epa.oszk.hu/04100/04185/00006/pdf/EPA04185_tudomany_es_hivatas_2020_02_042-052.pdf.

English translation archived via Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20997215>

Beyond the profane side of play¹

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Abstract

What is the ultimate purpose of play in terms of biology, ethology, or human ethology? To what extent is human play inherently profane? Can the duality of sacred and profane time and space be interpreted in relation to games as well? Furthermore, what role can a school game play within institutional and Christian education?

In this paper, I seek to answer these questions by drawing first on general ethology and then on human ethology, highlighting key concepts through specific examples and comparative descriptions. Next, utilizing the referenced literature, I briefly review the European variations of one of the oldest known games, hide-and-seek, incorporating representations from the fine arts and literary works. I conclude this historical overview with traditional Hungarian game descriptions. Finally, I provide a detailed analysis of a unique variant of hide-and-seek traditionally played within the schools of the Society of the Sacred Heart.

Keywords: hide-and-seek, Sacré Cœur, sacred, profane, educational goal

¹ This article is based on an expanded version (including illustrations) of the following study: Valentné Albert, Éva (2014). *A játék profán oldalán túl* [Beyond the profane side of play]. In: Fehér, Ágota; Fülöpné Erdő, Mária; Mészáros, László (eds.) *“In Caritate Perficias.” A keresztény nevelés mint társadalmi érték* [Christian Education as a Social Value]. Apor Vilmos Katolikus Főiskola, Vác, pp. 280–288.

What is the purpose of play from the perspective of biology, and more specifically, ethology? What is its role from the viewpoint of human ethology? To what extent is human play profane? Can the duality of sacred and profane time and space be interpreted in relation to play as well? What role can a school game play in education, or more specifically, in Christian education? In this paper, we seek answers to these questions, drawing initially on the fields of ethology and human ethology by highlighting and descriptively comparing specific examples. Subsequently, with the help of the referenced literature, we briefly review the European variants of one of the oldest traditional games, hide-and-seek, presenting examples from both the fine arts and literature. We conclude this historical overview with Hungarian game descriptions, followed by a detailed analysis of a unique variant played in the schools of the Society of the Sacred Heart. The course of the game has been reconstructed using the interview method alongside memoirs serving as primary sources. In the analysis, we address the differences and variations found within the game, identifying their unique educational content and exploring through them the manifestations of the dimension of play that lies beyond the profane.

1. **Figure** Goats at play at the Buffalo Reserve in Zalakomár, 2014.
(Photo by Zsolt Valent)

Play is not a human invention. In Vilmos Csányi's book *Etológia* (Ethology), we can read several examples of games occurring in the animal kingdom. Young fawns playing a game similar to "King of the Castle" (in Hungarian: "*Enyém a vár, tied a lekvár*") have been observed on numerous occasions. Standing on a small mound or hill, the fawn signals the start of the game by drumming its hooves. Then, the other fawns run up the hill and gently, "playfully", push down the one initially standing on top. When that fawn is removed from the hill, the one who pushed it off takes its place on top of the mound, and a new game begins. It is an important rule that no trace of aggression can be found. (Csányi 1994, 431).

What is the role of play in the animal kingdom? Is play merely a way for young animals to vent their surplus energy? According to Csányi, this idea does not hold ground. According to newer theories, play is much rather considered a form of training to develop muscles for later use. Could it possibly help practice certain behavioural patterns of adult life? If this were true, then individuals who are more skilled at play would be more effective at hunting as adults, but this is not the case. The purpose of play cannot be clearly explained from a biological standpoint. Its role, however, is manifold. Social play helps shape social behaviours and establish a hierarchy even among young individuals. Play allows the individual to test and combine the behavioural patterns they can generate; it acts as a mental cutting and assembling mechanism between biologically inherited and learned forms of behaviour. (Csányi 1994, 431–435).

The more important features of play include the following: it is mostly characteristic of young individuals; there is a play-soliciting signal or face, and there may also be a specific playful vocalization that inhibits the aggression of the playmate. After that, everything is just "for fun" or "pretend"... Sometimes it occurs with the involvement of objects (for instance, a raven lying on its back, repeatedly tossing up a small branch with its claws, and then trying to catch it with its beak). (Csányi 1994, 433–434).

2. **Figure** Male lion inviting to play (Csányi, 1994, p. 431).

From the field of human ethology, we will briefly demonstrate the culturally shaping role of play through two human tribes living in biologically similar environments but employing vastly different survival strategies, as presented in Csányi's cited

4. Figure Bushmen near Tsumkwe. Source: *The Vagabond Adventures, Bushmen Photo Diary*. Retrieved April 24, 2014, from <http://thevagabondadventures.com/us/tsumkwe/bushmen-photo-diary>

book, which references Eibl-Eibesfeldt's 1989 work. This work examines the differing educational and behavioural patterns of the Bushman (San) and Yanomamö tribes. It establishes that the Yanomamö, considered among the most warlike peoples, force their children into "martial" games at an early stage, where the goal is mutual physical abuse and defeat. Children who attempt to escape the game through tears are ridiculed and

3. Figure The Yanomami in Brazil. Source: *BR Wissen, Humanethologe Irenäus Eibl-Eibesfeldt*. Retrieved April 24, 2014, from <http://www.br.de/themen/wissen/humanethologe-irenaeus-eibl-eibesfeldt-100.html>

mocked. Consequently, they learn to endure pain at an early age and strive to meet expectations by defeating their "playmates" as effectively as possible. Conversely, the Bushmen do not encourage their children to engage in competitive games, but rather in those requiring cooperation, and they seek to resolve conflict situations as peacefully as possible. Although

resources are scarce for both tribes, adult Bushmen utilize cooperative techniques to manage this scarcity while maintaining modest agriculture, whereas the Brazilian Yanomamö seek to acquire scarce rainforest resources through constant warfare. In other words, games played during the early imprinting period can have a significant impact on certain forms of later aggression. (Csányi 1994, 707–708).

From this point of view, it is interesting to examine what modifications a particular type of game has undergone, as well as where and for what purpose it is played. What causes these differences? What kind of memory trace does it leave behind later? The subject of the present investigation is the game of hide-and-seek. Mentions of various forms of this game can be found in a Turkish book from Constantinople dating back to 1649, which describes a hiding game played among high-ranking nobles. (Paládi-Kovács 1988–2002, 643).

Earlier references and more detailed descriptions of games can be found in Endrei and Zolnay's work titled *Társasjáték és szórakozás a régi Európában* (Parlor Games and Entertainment in Old Europe). The authors classify hide-and-seek under the category of "Outdoor Games," specifically among "Seekers and Guessers." The simple form of hide-and-seek (*Cachette*), played primarily by children, rarely appears in historical accounts, although an example can be found in the childhood diary of Louis XIII (1601–1643). Shakespeare also mentions it as a children's game in 1598: "...an old infant play." (Shakespeare 1598/1886). For obvious reasons, descriptions of variants widespread among adults have been better preserved; one example is *Cutte cache* described by Rabelais (1494–1553), in which the other players guide the seeker of a hidden object with cues like "fire and water" or "hot and cold." Blindman's buff, as a variant of seeking games, can already be found among the ancient Greeks under the name "Copper Fly" (*Chalkē myia*). The blindfolded tagger attempts to catch the others while crying, "I am chasing a copper fly," to which they reply, "You are chasing it, but you will not catch it." The Scottish variant presumably dates back to the era of human sacrifice, where the player touched by the tagger was designated as "burned." The medieval French version, *Colin-Maillard*, evokes a knight from a battle fought in 999, who continued to strike down the enemy even after being blinded. (Endrei and Zolnay 1986, 79–81).

We quote Rabelais's atmospheric description from 1533, using the classic English translation by Thomas Urquhart and Peter Antony Motteux:

„I found them all recreating and diverting themselves at the play called muss, either before or after dinner; to me, truly, it is a thing altogether indifferent whether of the two it was, provided

that hic not., that the game of the muss is honest, healthful, ancient, and lawful, a Muscho inventore, de quo cod. de petit. haered. l. si post mortem. et Muscarii. Such as play and sport it at the muss are excusable in and by law, lib. 1. c. de excus. artific. lib. 10. And at the very same time was Master Tielman Picquet one of the players of that game of muss. There is nothing that I do better remember, for he laughed heartily when his fellow-members of the aforesaid judicial chamber spoiled their caps in swingeing of his shoulders.” (Rabelais 1533/1900, Book III, Chapter 40).

The French game named *Chapifou* (The Hood) derived its name from the practice of putting a headgear on the tagger backwards, while the other players removed their own hoods and used them to strike the tagger. This game, in which both genders participated, was highly popular among adults; it is referenced by several contemporary German poets, and accounts also exist of the Swedish King Gustavus Adolphus playing it with his colonels. A variant of the Hungarian game “*Erre csörög a dió*” (Rattling Nut) was described by Froissart (c. 1337 – c. 1405), in which players aided the tagger with the sound of small stones rattling inside seashells. A similar game is the French *Briché*, where a blindfolded participant sitting in the center touches one of the players with a stick, who then must speak in a distorted voice. If the tagger guesses their identity correctly, they switch places. This game frequently appears in various legal records, with its first mention dating back to 1270. Another variation, where the blindfolded tagger must strike and sometimes smash an object with a stick, is the Dutch game *Blind ei slaan* (Blind Egg-Striking). A variant of this game played with a clay pot can be found in Pieter Bruegel’s 1560 painting, *Children's Games*.

5. Figure Pieter Bruegel the Elder: *Children's Games* (1560), detail. Source: Wikimedia Commons. Retrieved April 24, 2014, from http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/e/e5/Pieter_Bruegel_d._%C3%84._041b.jpg

In the painting, the companion of the blindfolded tagger strikes the pot, providing directional cues to guide the seeker. A decree issued in 1428 permitted a similar game called *Hafen schlagen* (Pot-Striking; *Fazékverés* in Hungarian) in Nördlingen, and Rabelais also described it under the name *Casse-pot*. A similar game is *Saccomazzone*, which is well-known from Orazio Mochi's seventeenth-century sculpture.

6. **Figure** Orazio Mochi: *Saccomazzone* (1625). Source: Wikimedia Commons. Retrieved December 10, 2020, from https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Romolo_del_Tadda_e_orazio_mochi,_gioco_del_saccomazzone,_1613-20,_02.JPG

The series concludes with the game called “*Ki tette?*” (*Qui féry?*; Who did it?), an depiction of which can be found on a gold goldsmith's work belonging to Charles I of Anjou (1288–1342), King of Hungary. The tagger buries their face in the lap of one of the participants and places one hand behind their back (though the latter may be omitted depending on the context of the game); then, one of the players strikes it, and the tagger must guess who it was. (Endrei and Zolnay 1986, 79–81).

Following this European overview, let us examine the most common variations found in Hungary. According to the classification of *Magyar Néprajz* (Hungarian Ethnography), the game belongs to the category of "Intellectual Games," and more specifically, to "Hiding and Seeking Games." The book describes two primary variants. In *Sima bújócška* (Simple Hide-and-Seek), the tagger (*hunyo*, *humó*, or *kumó*) counts at a designated base while the other participants hide. The tagger then calls out: “*Aki bújt, bújt, aki nem, nem, (de én) megyek!*” (“Ready or not, here I come!”), and sets off to find the others. The first person found becomes the new tagger, while the remaining players come out of hiding on their own. In the *Ipi-apacs* variant, as soon as the tagger spots someone, they must race to a previously designated "home

tree" (*apacsfa*) and shout, for example: "Apacs a... [e.g., *Kis Pista*], *apacs, apacs, apacs!*" ("Apacs is... [player's name], *apacs, apacs, apacs!*"). However, if the tagger is careless, they themselves can be "tagged out" (*leapacsolják*) by a hider, forcing them to remain the tagger for the next round. A team-based version of hide-and-seek is known as *Katonázás* (Playing Soldiers). Members of one team act as taggers, while the other team hides. Upon locating a player, the seekers shout the hider's name, which eliminates them from the game. The round continues until every hider is found, after which the teams switch roles. To deceive the seekers, hidiers may exchange their clothes; if the seekers call out the wrong name, they are penalized by having to remain the seekers. *Magyar Néprajz* also places *Rabló-pandúr* (Cops and Robbers)—a game evoking the historical world of Hungarian outlaws (*betyárs*)—into this same category. (Paládi-Kovács 1988–2002, 643–644).

In the *Magyar gyermekjáték-gyűjtemény* (Collection of Hungarian Children's Games), published in 1891, Áron Kiss describes a variant of hide-and-seek called *Cigóra*. According to the account, this game is played exclusively by girls. One of them squats down in the center, while the others hold onto her skirt. Another girl walks around them reciting a rhyme, gradually lining up the girls standing in the circle behind herself. Once everyone has gathered behind her, they run away to hide—except for one girl, whose task is to cover the eyes of the tagger before she, too, goes into hiding. The tagger is referred to as the "devil," and the person they find first becomes the new devil. (Kiss 1891, 266).

Hedvig Justné Kéry presents the game in her work titled *Ősi és népi játékok élményfolyása és jelentőségük* (The Psychological Flow and Significance of Ancient and Folk Games) as follows. In hide-and-seek, there is typically one tagger and several hidiers. The identity of the tagger is decided by a counting-out rhyme. The tagger counts with closed eyes while the others hide. Subsequently, they set out to find the others, and anyone who is found must come out of hiding. The course of the game can be divided into two phases. The first is a danger-seeking activity. Hiding represents a form of protection, which no one leaves voluntarily. The second phase begins when this protection ceases, as the tagger uncovers the hiding spots. (Kéry 1975, 21).

The Dutch *bijócska* (hide-and-seek) is connected with springtime. It revives the tradition of young people searching for birds, flowers, and bugs, where the hidiers run from the "hunter" (seeker) while imitating the movements of birds. The *Ipiapacs* game involves a "safehouse". The seeker has to count here and then set out to find the others. The game consists of three parts. The first is hiding into a temporary place of safety; the second is leaving the hiding place to reach the "safehouse", bursting out of the secure state. The third is the end of the game:

finding all the players, and reaching a new and permanent safety in the "safehouse". "*Kinél van a sulykoló?*" (Who has the laundry bat?) is a Finnish game similar to *Ipiapacs*. The seeker counts to 50 at a rock, while the others hide. One of them holds an object, a *sulykoló* (a wooden laundry bat). Here, it is not enough to merely spot someone; the seeker also has to physically touch them. The goal of the game is finding the owner of the laundry bat. When this happens, the game ends: the owner of the laundry bat becomes the new seeker, and the old seeker becomes the new owner. If the owner of the laundry bat reaches the rock first and calls "*A fa hazakerült*" ("The wood has returned home"), then they are the winner, and the old seeker has to count again. The other players can help the owner of the laundry bat, and changing the hiding place after the countdown is allowed. (Kéry 1975, 20–23).

According to Kéry, the explanation for the game lies, on the one hand, in experiencing the danger of searching and discovery, and on the other hand, in the experience of separation and return—re-experiencing the child's fear of separation from the mother and the subsequent joy of finding and being found. (Kéry 1975, 31–32, 58).

We also present a special variation of this game, certain elements of which have been played in almost unchanged form and environment in the schools of the Sacré Cœur since the 1800s to this day. We quote from the memoir of a Sacré Cœur alumna, Márta Ádám:

"...and the *Cache-cache* is a team hide-and-seek. A young *mère*² was with every group; with rolled-up aprons, they ran with us across the entire house, hunting the opposing team. The one who caught three of them was the winner. At times, we were hiding, silent as the grave; at other times, the house shook with victorious cries. The winners received small gifts from the *mère* that they had made themselves, while the losers got a consolation prize. How much love, imagination, and work was behind it all." (Ádám 2005, 8–9).

Cache-cache means hide-and-seek in French. This particular variant has no name of its own, but it is highly similar to the *katonázás* (playing soldiers) mentioned above. We supplement this description based on the oral account of Márta Ádám. At the beginning of the game, two teams are formed. The team members are selected by the *mères*. First, one *mère* calls out a name, then the other, alternating until no children are left. They toss a coin to determine which team will be the seekers and which will be the hiders. Each team has a base. The duration of the hiding period is agreed upon in advance. While the hiding team conceals themselves, the

² *Mère* means Mother. It is a crucial distinction that the students addressed their teachers specifically as "Mother," rather than "Sister" or "Teacher," reflecting the unique familial spirit of the school.

seeker team waits at their own base. All members of the hiding team conceal themselves in the exact same location, occasionally in a classroom. Once the time is up, all members of the seeker team set out to find the other team. If they locate the hiding spot or room, they still have to gain entry somehow and touch at least three of the hidiers to claim victory. This part of the game often put a severe strain on the doors, as one team pushed from the inside while the other did the same from the outside. However, if at least three members of the hiding team managed to break out and reach their base, the hidiers won. The game was usually not repeated on the same day; it was timed for the period just before dinner, allowing the girls, exhausted from the excitement and running around, to rest during the meal.

Let us try to interpret this variant of the game from Kéry's point of view. Regarding the course of the game, the first important difference is that it is not merely about children playing together spontaneously; rather, we can speak of a game played in multiple teams by a collective of educators and children, taking place at a designated time and requiring prior preparation.

If we accept the explanation regarding the fear of separation and the joy of finding and being found—and indeed, why shouldn't we—then the variant played in the Sacré Cœur conveys important messages. The presence of the *mère*, the Mother, is permanent, even in times of danger, even at the very moment of hiding. One of the core principles of Christian education is realized through this game: you are never alone, you are never abandoned, the loving, protective caretaker is always with you... Likewise, the moment of victory is not about the solitude of a lonely victor or individual efficiency. It is a team that wins, with a Mother by its side. You are found, but not by a single person—rather, by a community. It is also essential that finding one or two people does not yet decide the game. It is symbolic that three individuals must be uncovered for the opposing team to achieve victory. The tension intensifies, but the player shares this tension with their own teammates, including the Mother.

According to the Sacré Cœur glossary³ found on the internet, which is quoted verbatim on the websites of several Sacré Cœur schools, *Cache-cache* is a variant of hide-and-seek traditionally played in Sacré Cœur schools to this day, with origins tracing back to the 1800s. It is highly probable that the game can be linked to the establishment of society and its early circumstances.

The Society of the Sacred Heart was founded on November 21, 1800, by Madeleine Sophie Barat (1779–1865), who was canonized in 1925 (Rébay 2002, 164). The Sacré Cœur is

³ *Sacré Cœur Glossary*: Available at: <https://sofie.org/resources/glossary/cache-cache> (Alternatively referenced via the US Province network at: <https://www.sacredheartusc.education/page/roots/resources/glossary>).

considered a female counterpart to the Jesuit Order. Due to the secularization during the French Revolution and the chaotic years that followed, the Jesuit Order had been suppressed. Although the exact backstory of the game is still a subject of research, it can be presumed that it reflects, on the one hand, the founders' secret existence and fear of persecution, while on the other, it may symbolize the poor children with whom the foundress started the school. Sister Erika Tornya RSCJ⁴ writes: "We are a religious order of Ignatian spirituality, founded in Paris in 1800 by Saint Madeleine Sophie. Paris was full of street children, whom Sophie and her companions gathered and raised."⁵ In other words, after being met and found, these children entered a safe environment filled with love.

The setting is also privileged—the sacred grounds of the school—as is the timing, occurring during a *Congé*⁶. The essence of the *Congé* is summarized by alumna Márta Ádám as follows:

"Congé: A day off, practically a playday. There were state holidays, such as the Governor's name day, the director's holiday, or a holiday granted by the Rev. Mère. Naturally, classes were suspended. On these days, anything went. Only the dormitories, washrooms, and the *Studiensaal* remained untouched in terms of *silence*. But there was no lining up; we could wander around and talk freely, at least when we weren't occupied with some game. We were still summoned to these games and to meals by the toll of the bell.

They were inexhaustible when it came to ideas. Once, they turned one of the classrooms into a magic cave. There was everything: a labyrinth constructed from benches and blankets, a full human skeleton borrowed from the science closet, a sea octopus... The latter was represented by a cloth glove stuffed with wet sand and moved about by who knows what mechanism. And the *cache-cache*..." (Ádám 2005, 8).

⁴ *Societas Religiosarum Sanctissimi Cordis Iesu* (RSCI) in Latin; *Religieuses du Sacré-Cœur de Jésus* (RSCJ) in French—meaning: Religious of the Sacred Heart of Jesus (Source: *Katolikus Lexikon*, <http://lexikon.katolikus.hu>).

⁵ See the interview with Sister Erika Tornya RSCJ on *Magyar Kurír*: <http://www.magyarkurir.hu/hirek/tornya-erika-szerzetesseg-nem-menekules-vilag-elol>

⁶ It is still called *Congé* to this day and is traditionally announced by the toll of a bell. The definition of the glossary explains: "On these special days, classes are cancelled in favor of a 'free day.' The word *congé* means 'leave' or 'holiday.' A tradition begun by St. Madeleine Sophie, *congés* come when they are least expected, since the planning for them is often done in secret." Because they are not always announced in advance, the joy is even greater when a *Congé* is declared on the morning of the day.

7. **Figure** Children playing at the Sophianum of the Sacré Coeur in Budapest, 1941. Photograph by Márta Ádám, alumna.

If the game takes place at a privileged time and in a privileged place, does it not become privileged by this very fact? Entering spaces where entry is otherwise forbidden or being allowed to shout in sacred and otherwise silent places—indeed, being allowed to shout at all—lends this game another dimension, a special experience, and a unique character.

When a game is played under such circumstances, can we speak of a dimension beyond the profane? According to Bakos's *Dictionary of Foreign Words and Phrases*, the word "profane" means: "1. uninitiated 2. secular, non-religious 3. common, everyday 4. disrespectful, sacrilegious 5. coarse, crude" (Bakos 1986, 684).

According to our research to date, this variant of the game is played exclusively in the schools of the Society of the Sacred Heart. Presumably, it is played this way in all 149⁷ of their schools and has likely been played so since their inception. It is as if the past students have not disappeared forever from these century-old corridors, and the sacred walls still echo with the triumphant shouts of their discovery...

⁷ *International Network of Sacred Heart Schools*. For the current global directory, see: <https://www.sacredheartusc.education/page/community/international-sacred-heart-schools> (Accessed: June 28, 2026).

Even the concept of community itself is not to be understood merely in its profane sense. Generation after generation, the students of Sacré Cœur schools form a sanctified community—not only through their participation in shared liturgies, but also because the time they spend together during their childhood constitutes a shared sacred time, and their school represents a shared sacred space. Consequently, their games also stand out, elevated above ordinary, everyday children's play. Ever since the canonization of the foundress, even the heavenly communion of saints seems closer, arriving within an almost tangible distance.

In his book *The Sacred and the Profane: The Nature of Religion*, Eliade distinguishes two modes of being in the world: one experienced by the religious person and its opposite, the profane mode. For the religious individual, any phenomenon in the world—including space and time—is saturated with the potential to manifest sacred realities. Eliade designates this manifestation of the sacred with the term *hierophany*. For the religious person, the object of a hierophany becomes something entirely different, whereas from a profane perspective, it remains exactly the same object it was before. For the believer, the space of a church is a hierophany, while a tourist lacking religious sentiment perceives only a world objectified into artistic values. (Eliade 1999, 7–10).

Connecting this line of thought with the team game played at the Sacré Cœur, we can conclude that the game itself can become a hierophany⁸, as can the entire community playing it. To further substantiate this, let us quote Bede the Venerable (672–735): "for the believer, play is to be embraced by Your [Jesus'] love." (Endrei and Zolnay 1986, 9). The game can help the religious person not only through the sacred space and sacred time detailed by Eliade, but also through the act of playing itself, allowing them "to become from time to time a contemporary of the gods." (Eliade 1999, 83).

The purpose of the game is clearly to strengthen the community—to deeply imprint a sense of mutual belonging through a profound experience of the feeling that *you are never alone, we are always with you, we will always find you*. The author of these lines caught a glimpse of this extraordinary communal experience when she mentioned that her great-grandmother had been a Sacré Cœur alumna. The former students turned toward her with the deep trust implied by the phrase: "You are our girl." Thus, it could be the subject of further research to examine how this community extends not only to its students but to their families as well; moreover, a sort of "perpetual membership" seems to absorb even the distant generations of an alumna's family.

⁸ From the Greek *hieros* (sacred) and *phainomai* (to manifest / to appear) (Eliade 1999, 7).

Perhaps play in a more general sense also possesses a dimension beyond the profane? Quoting Hans-Georg Gadamer, Tamás Nyíri writes the following about play: "There is always a certain to-and-fro movement that is not tied to any final goal where it would come to an end." Play also implies rules to which we subject ourselves while playing. According to Ernst Bloch, playing is "transformation, but within the certainty of holding one's ground." When bored, we ask ourselves, "What should I do?" and look for entertainment. Is the ultimate meaning of play simply entertainment? Free time is liberated time, not the time of "worry." "In free time, a human being is touched by the breath of that timeless, 'paradisiacal' protection, in the midst of which stands the tree of life." (Nyíri 1984, 657).

Do we play enough? Do we play with our children, whether as educators or as parents? What values do we instill in them while playing?

I. References

Ádám, M. (2005). *Kaleidoszkóp* [Kaleidoscope] [Unpublished manuscript].⁹

Bakos, F. (1986). *Idegen szavak és kifejezések szótára* [Dictionary of foreign words and phrases]. Akadémiai Kiadó.

Csányi, V. (1994). *Etológia* [Ethology]. Nemzeti Tankönyvkiadó.

Eliade, M. (1999). *A szent és a profán* [The sacred and the profane] (T. Berényi, Trans.). Európa Könyvkiadó.

Endrei, W., & Zolnay, L. (1986). *Társasjáték és szórakozás a régi Európában* [Board games and entertainment in old Europe]. Magvető Könyvkiadó.

Justné Kéry, H. (1975). *Ősi és népi játékok élménylefolyása és jelentőségük* [The experiential process and significance of ancient and folk games]. Akadémiai Kiadó.

Kiss, Á. (2000). *Magyar gyermekjáték-gyűjtemény* [Collection of Hungarian children's games] (Original work published 1891). Magyar Elektronikus Könyvtár. Retrieved February 15, 2014, from <http://mek.oszk.hu/10800/10818/10818.pdf>

⁹ This source is published as an appendix (pp. 214–236) in the following doctoral dissertation: Valentné Albert, É. (2019). *Iskolai narratívumok Sacré Coeur növendékek élettörténetében* [School narratives in the life histories of Sacré Coeur alumnae] (Doctoral dissertation, Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, Hungary). ELTE Digital Institutional Repository. Retrieved December 4, 2020, from <https://edit.elte.hu/xmlui/handle/10831/49540>
<https://doi.org/10.15476/ELTE.2019.031>

Nyíri, T. (1984). A gyermek az antropológia szemszögéből [The child from an anthropological perspective]. *Vigilia*, 49(9), 651–660.

Paládi-Kovács, A. (Ed.). (1988–2002). *Magyar Néprajz* [Hungarian Ethnography]. Akadémiai Kiadó. Retrieved February 15, 2014, from <http://vmek.oszk.hu/02100/02152/html/06/103.html>

Rabelais, F. (1900). *The works of Rabelais: The Third Book* (Chapter XL) (Original work published 1546). London: Published for the trade. Retrieved July 12, 2018, from https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/The_Third_Book/Chapter_XL

Rébay, M. (2002). A Sacré Coeur Magyarországon 1883-1950 [The Sacré Coeur in Hungary 1883-1950]. In G. Fejérdy (Ed.), *Tanulmányok fél évezred magyar történelméből* [Studies from half a millennium of Hungarian history] (pp. 164–196). Pázmány Péter Katolikus Egyetem.

Shakespeare, W. (1997). *Love's labour's lost* (Etext No. 1109) (Original work published 1595). Project Gutenberg. Retrieved July 12, 2018, from <http://www.gutenberg.org/cache/epub/1109/pg1109.html>

Tornya, E. (n.d.). *A szerzetesség nem menekülés a világ elől* [Monasticism is not an escape from the world]. Magyar Kurír Katolikus Hírportál. Retrieved January 11, 2014, from <http://www.magyarkurir.hu/hirek/tornya-erika-szerzetesseg-nemmenekules-vilag-elol>

Lexicons, glossaries, and data. Retrieved August 15, 2018, from

* <http://www.lexikon.katolikus.hu>

* <https://www.sacredheartusc.education/page/community/international-sacred-heart-schools>

* <https://www.sacredheartusc.education/page/roots/resources/glossary>¹⁰

¹⁰ The original URL specified in 2013 (sofie.org/schools/international) has been updated to mirror the official live portal of the international network configuration database.